

This observational ecological study aimed to identify factors that may affect COVID-19 testing and positivity rates in rural communities in West Virginia. Researchers assessed data obtained from West Virginia Health and Human Resources and Census data. COVID-19 PCR testing data was combined with Census data to study the relationship between COVID-19 testing, positivity rates, and socioeconomics. Researchers aimed to identify high risk communities and vulnerable populations in West Virginia in need of stronger testing approaches.

WHERE

State of West Virginia

WHEN?

March 2020 – September 2020

THE POPULATION

- This was an observational ecological study. Data from West Virginia Health and Human Resources and census tract data were used. Participants were not actively recruited.

WHAT HAPPENED

- COVID-19 PCR testing data collected from March 2020 to September 2020 was used to assess testing and positivity rates. Data included test results from testing locations across the state.
 - Data included a unique identifier, zip code, date, type of test, and test result for each person.
- Census data included information by census tract.
 - Data included race, level of food insecurity, type of area (rural, urban, etc.), and Area Deprivation Index score.
- GIS analysis was used to develop maps showing where key variables were distributed throughout the state.
- Spatial regression analyses were conducted to identify adjusted risk for COVID testing and positivity at the tract level.

KEY FINDINGS

1. Small clusters of COVID positivity were found throughout the state, with higher rates in Mideastern and Southwestern West Virginia.
2. Higher rates of positive COVID-19 PCR tests were found in areas with higher food insecurity and lower populations of Black residents
3. Higher testing rates were found in rural areas with higher food insecurity and lower populations of Black residents

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

- **Observational Ecological study** study used to measure prevalence and incidence of disease at the population or group level.
- **Area Deprivation Index** an evaluation of a region's socioeconomic conditions that have been linked to health outcomes. Can be reported as a score or percentile.
- **Census Tract** a geographic region within the limits of a city, town, or county. Usually defined for the purpose of the census.
- **Food insecurity** lack of reliable availability and/or access to enough affordable, nutritious food.

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